

A SIMPLE CLASSIFICATION OF ENGLISH UNSTRESSED VOWEL PHONOLOGICAL OPPOSITIONS

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Vowel sounds in English are distinguished by three phonological features. They are the features relating to: a) vertical movements of the tongue, b) horizontal movements of the tongue and c) the qualitative and quantitative (long-short) characteristics of vowels. On the basis of these distinctive features, vowel phonemes form the phonological oppositions. The phonological oppositions of vowel phonemes in English are classified by V.A.Vassilyev and A.A.Abduezizov, in which mainly the stressed position of vowels is dealt. Since in these classifications the vowel oppositions are classified only in terms of the number of phonological distinctive features in one opposition, they can be included in the simple classifications of phonological oppositions. V.A.Vassilyev, taking into consideration the number of phonological distinctive features in one opposition of English vowels, classified them as follows: a) single opposition; b) double opposition; c) plural opposition, which is distinguished by more than two phonological characters. [6, 183-194]. A.Abduezizov combined English vowels into the oppositions that differ by one feature according to the horizontal movement of the tongue. He gave nine examples of vowel oppositions according to the vertical movement of the tongue and noted that these oppositions also differ by one feature, but if the qualitative and quantitative features of vowels are taken into consideration, most of these oppositions differ by two features [1, 124-125]. In English, vowel phonemes can also be distinguished by three features in one opposition. For example, the phonemes /ɑ:/, /ʌ/, which distinguish the words dark /dɑ:k/ - duck /dʌk/, differ from each other according to the distinctive features relating to the horizontal movement of the tongue, the vertical movement of the tongue and the qualitative and quantitative (long-short) characteristics of vowels. Thus, in English, the oppositions of vowel phonemes in the stressed position are divided into the following three subgroups depending on the number of distinctive features in one phonological opposition: a) single opposition, which is distinguished by one distinctive feature; b) double opposition, which is distinguished by two distinctive features; c) triple opposition, which is distinguished by three distinctive features.

In order to determine if the classification mentioned above is true or not in the unstressed positions, we applied it to unstressed vowels and achieved the following results :

Unstressed vowels, like stressed ones, are distinguished by either horizontal or vertical movement of the tongue in single oppositions. For example:

/ə-ʌ/ – mixed - back-advanced: some /səm/ (pr.) - some /sʌm/ (adj.) [1, 123];

In double oppositions, the unstressed vowels are distinguished by both horizontal and vertical movements of the tongue, as well as by either horizontal or vertical movement of the tongue and the quantitative (long-short) feature of vowels in one opposition. Examples of this are the following oppositions:

/ə - ɪ/ – mixed - front-retracted, mid-open (broad variation) - close (broad variation): pepper [ˈpepə] - peppy [ˈpepi];

/ə - e/ – mixed - front, mid-open (broad variation) - mid-open (narrow variation): supplement [ˈsʌplɪmənt] n. - supplement [ˈsʌplɪmənt] v.;

/ə - u:/ – mixed - back, mid-open (broad variation) - close (narrow variation): cooker [ˈkukə] - cuckoo [ˈkuku:];

/ə - ɑ:/ – mixed - back, mid-open (broad variation) - open (broad variation): forum [ˈfɔ:rəm] - fore-arm [ˈfɔ:rɑ:m] n.;

/ɪ - ʌ/ – front-retracted - back-advanced, close (broad variation) - mid-open (broad variation): enable [ɪˈneɪbl] - unable [ʌnˈeɪbl];

/ɪ - ɔ:/ – front-retracted - back, close (broad variation) - open (narrow variation): innate [ɪˈneɪt] - ornate [ɔ:ˈneɪt];

/ɪ - ɒ/ – front-retracted - back, close (broad variation) - open (wide variation): inside [ɪnˈsaɪd] - onside [ɒnˈsaɪd];

/ɪ - æ/ – front-retracted - front, close (broad variation) - open (broad variation): catnip [ˈkætnɪp] - catnap [ˈkætnæp];

/ɪ - u:/ – front-retracted - back, close (broad variation) - close (narrow variation): cookie [ˈkuki] - cuckoo [ˈkuku:];

/ɔ: - ɜ:/ – back - mixed, open (narrow variation) - mid-open (narrow variation): export [ˈekspɔ:t] - expert [ˈekspɜ:t];

/ɔ: - ʊ/ – back - back-advanced, open (narrow variation) - close (broad variation): outport [ˈaʊtpɔ:t] - output [ˈaʊtpʊt];

/ʌ - e/ – back-advanced - front, mid-open (broad variation) - mid-open (narrow variation): unlisted [ʌnˈlɪstɪd] - enlisted [enˈlɪstɪd];

/ɒ - i:/ – back - front, open (wide variation) - close (narrow variation): proton [ˈprəʊtɒn] - protein [ˈprəʊti:n];

/ə - ɜ:/ – mid-open (broad variation) - mid-open (narrow variation), short - long (quality and quantity feature): forward [ˈfɔ:wəd] - foreword [ˈfɔ:wɜ:d].

In triple oppositions, the unstressed vowels are distinguished by all the three distinctive features such as the horizontal movement of the tongue, the vertical movement of the tongue, and the qualitative-quantitative characteristics of vowels in one phonological opposition. For example:

/i: - ɪ/ – front – front-retracted, close (narrow variation) - close (broad variation), the qualitative-quantitative features of vowels (long-short): forefeet [ˈfɔ:fi:t] n. - forfeit [ˈfɔ:fit] v.

/ə - ɔ:/ – mixed - back, mid-open (broad variation) - open (narrow variation): addition [əˈdɪʃn] - audition [ɔ:ˈdɪʃn];

The above examples show that the vowel oppositions in English can be distinguished by up to three distinctive features even in the unstressed positions. Thus, the oppositions of unstressed vowels can be classified as follows according to the number of distinctive features in one opposition:

- a) single opposition, which is distinguished by one distinctive feature;
- b) double opposition, which is distinguished by two distinctive features;
- c) triple opposition, which is distinguished by three distinctive features.

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